

NOTE ON WHY GZ IS FUNDAMENTALLY NOT RIGHTING ARM

Genick Bar–Meir

Potto Project

Skokie, Illinois 60076

Email: barmeir at gmail dot com

ORCID: 0000-0003-3285-7837

ABSTRACT

The righting arm is a fundamental quantity that controls the rolling and pitching motions and is required to write the governing equations. Using the Lagrangian mechanics (as opposed to Newtonian mechanics), it was shown that the righting arm is not GZ . For over 200 years, engineers have described the righting arm for the roll and pitch simply by $GM \sin \theta$ as obvious and simple. The physics dictates that the torque is made from two skewed identical forces times the distance between these forces. In this case, like everything in marine engineering, the establishment's ideas in marine engineering are wrong. This erroneous idea is typical of all the errors in the field. Yet, the distance between these two forces is based on Bouguer's diagram, which has a major error which actually was well known even to Bouguer.

Recently, the correct distance was found using the Lagrangian method. Currently, this distance interpretation is done using the standard Newtonian mechanics. The wrong distance between the couple forces rendered almost all the research work based on the previous idea, at best, useless. All the calculations based on the establishment's model GZ have to be disregarded.

NOMENCLATURE

Points of Interest

\mathcal{A} Pivot point at the liquid level

\mathcal{B} Buoyancy centroid

G Mass centroid

GM Distance between \mathcal{M} and G

\mathcal{M} Metacenter none existent and imaginary point

Z A point on GM perpendicular to \mathcal{B}'

Variables

g Gravity constant

h Height above the roll axis of the location considered

I Moment of inertia of body and liquid

\mathcal{RA} righting arm

Greek Letters

ω The ship roll period

θ Characteristic roll amplitude

Key Words

Righting Arm, Ship Navigation, Why wrong ideas entrenched?, Added Moment of Inertia, Pivot Point locations

1 Introduction

The governing equation that deals the rolling has four components which include: the internal forces, damping forces, the righting forces, and the exterior forces. The internal forces, typically are written as $I d^2\theta/dt$ which is wrong and it was discussed (Bar-Meir 2023f). Also moment of inertia, I (body and added) depends on pivot point (why this point controversial?). The damping forces related to the

first derivative of θ with coefficients that related to other parameters while there is disagreement about it. First, the pivot point has to be located, and second the right mechanism has to be determined (notice the transition to turbulence is moot as it is quasi steady state and some elements/zones in the laminar regime bit the turbulence is established.). The righting forces are related to the $GM \sin \theta$ according to the leading establishment's "scientists". The exterior forces are described by various and some time conflicting ideas. This paper deals with the righting arm and reforms the establishment's idea which is wrong. The added mass understanding to a large extend was described (Bar-Meir 2023c; Bar-Meir 2022a; Bar-Meir 2022e; Bar-Meir 2024a; Bar-Meir 2023e; Bar-Meir 2023d; Bar-Meir 2023c; Bar-Meir 2023b; Bar-Meir 2023a; Bar-Meir 2023f; Bar-Meir 2023g; Bar-Meir 2022c; Bar-Meir 2022d; Bar-Meir 2024a; Bar-Meir 2024b; Bar-Meir 2024b; Bar-Meir and Altschul 2024; Bar-Meir 2022b). Elgar (1884) explicitly state the following:

Quotations

W being the weight of the ship. But $GZ=MG \sin \theta$; and therefore when $WOWT$ is indefinitely small, the righting moment is proportional to $X MG$. While G remains below M the moment is always a righting one

Reference: Elgar, Francis 1884

The notation is explained in fig. 1 for this quotation. This point was not found in the earlier references, to say that either it was not explicit or not visible enough for this author. Nevertheless that was the perception of all with no exception to view this righting length for the moment couple. This length is analysed here with possible explanation why people got it wrong.

In ~1750 Euler suggested equation for the metacentric radius and other issue. Unfortunately, Euler could not save Bouguer's idea of metacentric and thus, Atwood continued in the same path introducing the calculations for the righting arm. Atwood (1796) published a method calculating the righting arm for based on the shifted wedge volume method. He also mentioned the term GZ (who is the first to use landmark Z ?).

In 1870 two ships experienced the same storm. While HMS Captain (one ship) with $GM = 0.79[m]$ capsized while the other ship with similar GM ($0.73[m]$) escaped the

fate and survived. To all the engineers, which lack of dimensional analysis knowledge, it was a surprised¹. Note that other parameters were different such as the raft (freeboard). This event provide hint that something wrong with trusting the GM . Hence, some start to promote the GZ as they were not able to use the dimensional analysis.

This disaster suggested that something is wrong with the metacentric height is insufficient measure of the ship safety. The additional information is needed and since the lack of dimensional analysis could be used a derivative of GM that added additional input. This action is typical example of when the current "science" does not provide answer. This shortage popularize the righting arm or GZ diagram (see for example (Reed 1885)) yet, the most important landmark was missing (point A).

It is not surprising that this error, GZ , is added to the long list of fundamental errors used by the people in the field. Obviously, this error like many other in this field render the "scientific" works in the field to be less than worthless papers dealing the rotation(s). This list deals only with errors related to rolling motion

- ☞ Usage of $(I_{body} + I_{44}) d\theta/dt$ where there three mistakes I_{body} not defined correctly, I_{44} does not exist or defined, the right equation should be $d((I_{body} + I_{added}) \theta) / dt$
- ☞ The right arm is not $GM \sin \theta$ as M is not at a fixed location.
- ☞ In wavy liquid, the oblique liquid line should be considered.
- ☞ The difference of the effective draft affecting the rolling.
- ☞ The rolling is not affected by any m_{ij} type parameter due to coupling or other wise.
- ☞ Conflating the added mass properties with the transfer properties. Only minor discussions address this point appear by this author, the only person that study this issue.
- ☞ Usage of the wrong implementation of the strip theory.
- ☞ The pivot point locations (varieties of issues).

The metacentric method leads to a righting arm of $GM \sin \theta$, as stated by Elgar, it must be perpendicular. The metacentric method was almost exclusive stability analysis

¹Even today most, if not all, engineers in this area are not familiar with knowledge of dimensional analysis

FIGURE 1. Schematic for construction of the **GM**, Notice that the angle WOW is equal to the angle BMB , as it was the perception until the publication the first paper in “Simplified Rolling Calculations” by this author. This figure originally was drawn with white lines on black canvas the transformation might not be perfectly match. Clearly, the exhibit is after Elgar (1884) figure 1.

until 1990 when the introduction or (implementation) of the potential method (Erdős, Schibler, and Herndon 1992). The “new” approach (Erdős, Schibler, and Herndon 1992) is based on the idea by Huygens (1967) potential stability which does not consider the angles and such. Thus, the salvation did not come-out from that method (at least not yet). The last approach is the angle in angle out (AIAO) which focus on the angles and the pivot locations invented by this author. In fact, this method leads to so many advances in the marine engineering that fundamentally change the whole field.

This field of ship stability/navigation is one of the oldest engineering discipline and can be traced its roots to Archimedes and others from that era. It can be argue that this field attracted the most lucid individuals, just to name a few, L. Euler, D. Bernoulli, Pierre Bouguer, William Froude, Osborne Reynolds and etc. This field has fostered many advances in mathematics like perturbation methods, numerical methods (Bouguer’s trapezoid integration method for example), etc. With all these incredible individuals one cannot wonder why so many errors where introduced into this field? One of these fundamental errors is the righting arm. Thus, without the correct righting arm there is no way to calculate the frequencies of the ship for instance.

A disputation was issued several years ago, and no one dares to defend the establishment’s ideas only many are asking not to have their papers reviewed. For example, Metin Taylan asked or a better word demanded that no dis-

cussion will be done about his papers and they should be keep in a “vault”. The definition of author in the scientific community, beside writing the intellectual idea, is to defend these ideas which he or she present. If author is not willing to defend his or her idea this author should consider not writing any scientific papers. That is the reason that the author address is printed on title page, otherwise it is just a joke. It is dystopian to see people publish papers which they have known to be faulty and they cannot defend their paper. Or at least, show the logic behind their work.

2 Is The Metacenter Has A Fatal Error?

FIGURE 2. Metacentric curve schematic with specific angles to show pro-metacentric points for that specific angle. After Reed 1885 page 15 figure 13.

Bouguer and many others realized that the metacentric point is not “seating” in a fix location but moves in both directions (x and y) (see for example fig. 2). Yet, when the term **GM** was used in stability/navigation calculations and it was assumed to be constant (hence $GZ = GM \sin \theta$). People try to overcome and compensate this problem by asserting that the graph of **GZ** for every ship or floating body is good representation. Interesting, this graph should be depended on the ship draft (how much ship in the liquid/water), the list (bow and stern parts in the liquid, equilibrium pitch point), and the pivot point. The **GZ** calculations, from the initial point, should not be based on either pivot point at the metacenter or mass centroid. Hence, all calculations of the **GZ** that have been done fundamentally wrong because they used the wrong the pivot point. This what the establishment’s “scientists” have done. This practice of using erroneous concepts is so entrenched in the marine engineering that is mind-boggling.

To emphasis this point, this issue was brought to the attention of Chris Kent assistant editor later he demanded

that his journal or other establishment’s journal approved these “radical” idea. He also was asked to show/provide even a single paper in his journal that does not violate the second laws of thermodynamics which he failed to do. His inability to provide even a single example article without violations of second law of thermodynamics is frightening. What are these editors doing just filtering the good stuff out? Shame!

FIGURE 3. The actual metacentric curve schematic for specific angles. It show the dramatic change on the metacentric point for small angles in y and small in x direction. After Reed (1885)

In this discussion, the concept rsymmetry was mentioned. Some ships are designed so that they are not rsymmetrical for various reasons (rsymmetry is issue related rotational horizontal moving of pivot point.). The metacentric methods simply does not have provision or even recognize this possibility. How one even can calculate any thing when the method does not recognize that possibility? Obviously, over ten (10) billion dollars in grants and constructions are spent on these nonsense ideas does bother the establishment.

The publications of (Bar-Meir 2023f) demonstrated that the GZ the righting arm is erroneous at least in the way it is used ($GM \sin \theta$). The work based on Lagrangian mechanics abstracted the misperception (due Bouguer’s description) of ship geometry and get straight the correct equation. The fundamental and main confusion in the

metacentric method was due to ignoring the moving of the metacentric point see fig. 3. In fig. 1 the two angles, angle in and angle out, are the same which is deceiving as if the pivot point is at the mass centroid the angles cannot be the same i.e. angle in not equal the angle out. Notice yet in the same publication Reed in his drawing shows that the pivot point is at metacenter which is moving. While the schizophrenic approach with two different pivot points appeared in many of the publications of that era. To keep the same displaced volume the drawing shows pivot point at \mathcal{A} while claiming that the pivot point is at \mathcal{M} . In the drawing like Elgar² where diagram has a pivot point at the definition \mathcal{A} (center of liquid line), yet in the discussion the pivot point is at \mathcal{M} . This duality (or more) leads many to believe in metacenter as the pivot point.

The reason that this “fact” seems to be proper is because metacenter, \mathcal{M} , seem to be meaningless without being the pivot point. No one noticed that the angles in and out are not the same. This deception has been accepted with numerous disputes and the arguments about whether \mathcal{M} is above the water line or metacentric curve geometry (points increasing inclination angle different location M_1, \dots, M_5 ³ etc. see for example Elgar and Reed more discussions on this point.). The cardinal question is if the angles are not the same; is there a way to calculate the distance (the actual distance between the two action lines)? Clearly, the notation of GZ is not appropriate in this case. The answer yes, it can be done but it is very complicated. It is similar to touching the nose after circling the head twice.

One of the characterizing of the metacentric method is the sole effect of the surface without taking into account the “future” shape of the ship. As compare to AIAO method which takes into account the “future”. For example, isosceles triangle placed into two different situations upside and downside. Clearly the draft would be different scenarios: top part placed in the liquid have a larger draft while the bottom part placed in liquid has a smaller draft. The metacentric method really does not recognize the change of the angles from the surface area to a smaller width or larger (as in the case opposite triangle). Notice that in metacentric submerged volume is the same for both cases. The AIAO recognises the rsymmetrical nature of this difference and the stability indication is calculated. In fact

²see for example, Elgar’s diagram

³The subscript is reference to angle such as M_5 is M for 5° .

this idea was not noticed in the last 300 years.

3 Metacenter Calculations the Righting Arm

In diagram fig. 1 the distance righting arm is $GM \sin \theta$. This distance is not the distance for the angle at hand but GM_0 as for pro-metacentric point for zero angle. The almost actual distance $GM_i \sin \theta$ where i refers to the angle. Notice that this expression is also in a need for correction to account for the angle (perpendicular) to mass centroid G . This fact did not appear or was visible in the literature.

FIGURE 4. Pawlowski’s diagram for calculating the GZ . It can be observed that the displacement is not constant according to illustration as two triangles are not equal. The head point for both triangles is not on the symmetry line.

To demonstrate these points a relatively recent paper by Pawlowski (2017) is analysed. There several versions of the paper and the one selected as in title “Technical Report No. 72 The Stability of a Freely Floating Ship” the second version Final report. While this paper is poorly written⁴, it provide important information about the lack of understanding of the establishment. The abstract start with “[t]he report presents the problem of calculating the righting arms (GZ -curve) for a freely floating ship, longitudinally balanced at each heel angle.” For paper of about 60 pages, one expects, to some understanding. For example, the buoyancy must be constant where the two triangles

head is not on the symmetry line because the pivot point is at G .

Pawlowski claims that the change of the trim (change of the zero or neutral pitch “low stern or bow”) creates a large change in the GZ graph. This change is caused by the asymmetric structure of the ship. If there is an asymmetry in the ship body it automatically means the ship not rsymmetrical and any calculations is defective because the change of the pivot point cause the horizontal movement of buoyancy location. While giving credit to author because misstatements and attribute these statement the author poor English, (in the term poor English it meant that terms are combined but with out clear meaning)

Quotations

Longitudinal balance occurs when the centre of buoyancy is at a vertical plane, termed the plane of rotation, passing through the centre of ship gravity.

Reference: Pawlowski, 2017

Can anyone explain these statements really mean? While it can be guessed but say precisely that the author meant isn’t possible. This paper is example of incoherent way things getting, and one wonder if it done purposely to abstract the GZ topic.

4 The Righting Arm

The righting arm depends on several factors and in this section the search is on factors that do not change due do the angle change. The meaning of this statement is $RA \neq f(\theta)$ where RA is the right arm. The term GZ is not appropriate as it describe erroneous right arm.

In this recognition, the distance one sought to get is the distance between B' to G in the inclination angel component. This distance should be calculated based on fixed locations or fixed distances i.e. no involvement of the M . This distance is made from two distances one the purple color which states $AG \sin \theta$ which one part. The second distance is B' between B'' . The angle α is function of the θ and the geometry. Basically from the geometry description in fig. 5 it can be written as

$$RA = B'B'' + AG \sin \theta \quad (1)$$

⁴For example the author use the notation “free trim” but it is not defined in the paper
doi:10.5281/zenodo.15033768
Vol:2025 No:119 March, 2025

metacenter or mass centroid or “rolling center”. The rolling center mentioned in this paper. Or pivot point is somewhere strange like 1/3 distance between x to y.

2. The moment of inertia is independent of the pivot point.
3. Added mass or the added moment of inertia is constant.
4. The pivot point is constant in the ship navigation equations.
5. If you believe that MMG equations are correct.
6. If you believe the traditional strip theory as it is described in MIT’s class.
7. If you believe that added mass is not actually a single added mass at least for the translational movement.
8. If you believe that more 20% of the world research in the ship stability navigation does not violate the second law of thermodynamics.

Acknowledgment

This paper describe progress in this magnitude has some willing and unwilling partners (some of the exposed and some not). First, thank you for Marry Jolimatizc who correct the English of early draft. Second, the unwilling participants such as Carolyn Q. Judge from USNA that set to “protect” her students from the truth and the minion. Also Spyrou by his plagiarizing demonstrated how the establishment deals with the “rogue agent” by netscaping their material.

About the Author

As opposed to many other researchers, this author does not brag about how many citations his work has or jobs he held but only points to how many breakthroughs he has made and on how many people plagiarized his work. In the die casting industry, he has revolutionized the field by solving several major open questions. These questions include the critical plunger velocity, pQ^2 diagram, intensification pressure and critical vent area etc (for those who not familiar with die casting, these are the main pliers of die casting.). It has to be mentioned that the die casting establishment believed in solutions which violated the second law of the thermo and has spent millions promoting these beliefs (like the woke religion). Since the problems were not solved, literally hundreds of CFD teams from all over the world attempted to solve the problem in vain where this author solved them. The establishment fought against publishing

these discoveries. The irony is that these author’s models today are undisputed and accepted in the industry.

Furthermore, this servant solved several open problems in shock dynamics and potential of compressed substances. Additionally, this author solved the deep ocean pressure and speed of sound which many oceanographers failed to calculate (Pushka Equation).

Bar–Meir was instrumental in developments of the added mass (properties) concepts. He differentiate between the added properties and the transfer properties. He discovered the change of the added mass (the general form) and its effects on the governing equations. He invented the stability dome for floating bodies and in the process developed the equation for location of centroid of circle segment.

Kostas J. Spyrou, when he gave his keynote lecture, basically copied many concepts that were developed by Bar–Meir (such as the stability dome) and presented them as his ideas. These concepts had never appeared in the literature before. It is interesting to point out that Dr. Spyrou has been observed downloading Bar–Meir’s book. Dr. Spyrou’s behavior is not unique to him only. Dr. Kenneth Brezinsky went out of his way to declare that Bar–Meir’s calculations of compressible gas potential were useless and baseless. However, Brian J. Cantwell from Stanford University recently decided to copy Bar–Meir’s idea and to dedicate a whole section (2.9) to it in his book (and probably also in his classes). Except that Dr. Cantwell oversimplified the idea (he removed the dimensionless presentation), maybe because he did not fully understand it. The ship stability went major revision and basically revamped the field in particular the added mass (properties). The old governing equations yielding hundreds percent errors had to be modified due to discoveries by this author.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar–Meir certify that he has NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity or person with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers’ bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials or individuals discussed in this manuscript.

REFERENCES

- Atwood, G. (1796). The construction and analysis of geometrical propositions, determining the positions assumed by homogeneous bodies which float freely, and at rest, on a fluid's surface; also determining the stability of ships, and of other floating bodies. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London na*(86), 46–130.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2022a, April). *Basics of Fluid Mechanics* (0.6.2 ed.). Potto Project Publishing. doi:10.5281/zenodo.5521908.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2022b). Novel approach to aquatic bodies locomotion and review of current state: Part 1. *Potto Project Publications 2020*, 36–42. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6528763.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2022c, May). Novel approach to aquatic bodies locomotion and review of current state: Part 2 analytical solution. *Potto Project Publications 2022*, 78–84. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6554877.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2022d, July). Novel approach to aquatic bodies locomotion: Part 3: Pectoral fin source of power. *Potto Project Publications 2022*, 92–99. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6712269.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2022e, Nov). *Stability of Ships and Other Bodies* (0.8.2 ed.). Potto Project Publishing. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6462156.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2023a, July). Boundary conditions and their effects on the added mass. *Potto Project Publications 2023*, 43–52. doi:10.5281/zenodo.8137153.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2023b, April). Centroid of the added mass and its effects on governing equations. *Potto Project Publications 2023*, 74–79. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7823666.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2023c, May). The change of the added mass and its effects on governing equations version 2. *Potto Project Publications 2023*, 23–31. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7851105.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2023d, march). The governing equations of surface vessels and aquatic bodies: Why people get it wrong? *potto project Publications 2023*, 14–18. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7706893.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2023e, August). A note why added mass concept is mathematically needed. doi:10.5281/zenodo.15033768
- Potto Project Publications 2023*, 53–56. doi:10.5281/zenodo.8218088.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2023f, October). Simplified rolling calculations: Part 1 the basics. *Potto Project Publications 2023*, 34–48. doi:10.5281/zenodo.10030144.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2023g, Nov). *Stability of Ships and Other Bodies* (0.8.5 ed.). Potto Project Publishing. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6622208.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2024a, April). Simplified rolling calculations: Part 2 the horizontal moving pivot point. *Potto Project Publications 2024*, 4–22. doi:10.5281/zenodo.10030144.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2024b, May). Simplified rolling calculations: Part 3 the coupling of degrees of freedom. *Potto Project Publications 2024*, 14–27. doi:10.5281/zenodo.11360944.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2024a, January). Literature review of recent navigation and stability of ship. *Potto Project Publications 2024*, 4–13. doi:10.5281/zenodo.10467538.
- Bar-Meir, G. (2024b, Oct). Simplified rolling calculations: Part 4 an example of coupling 2 degree of freedom (dof) or more. *Potto Project Publications 2024*, 41–56. doi:10.5281/zenodo.13930784.
- Bar-Meir, G. and L. Altschul (2024, July). Comparison between **AG** and **GM** and literature review. *Potto Project Publications 2024*, 53–65. doi:10.5281/zenodo.13146118.
- Elgar, F. (1884). The variation of stability with draught of water in ships. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London 37*(232-234), 205–229.
- Erdős, P., G. Schibler, and R. C. Herndon (1992). Floating equilibrium of symmetrical objects and the breaking of symmetry. part 1: Prisms. *American journal of physics 60*(4), 335–345.
- Huygens, C. (original 1650 reprint 1967). *De iis quae liquido supernatant libri tres* (“Three books on bodies floating on top of a liquid”), Volume XI, 1908. Amsterdam: Republished Swets and Zeitlinger.
- Pawłowski, M. (2017). The stability of a freely floating ship. *International Journal of Maritime Engineering 159*(A1), 1–59.
- Reed, E. J. (1885). *A Treatise on the Stability of Ships*. C. Griffin.